

Enhancing the User Interface of Clubhouse Mobile Application

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Abstract: This research examines how usability and human-computer interaction (HCI) principles and guidelines were applied to the redevelopment of Clubhouse, an excellent social-audio mobile application. The poor usability of many apps, as well as the lack of application of HCI concepts and guidelines, wastes time and frustrates users. Because a functional mobile application is critical in today's social media industry, application design has been extensively researched, resulting in the publication of a variety of design guides. Designers will still need their knowledge and intuition to construct an application because these tips do not provide a particular design technique. Most social media apps on the market now imitate or have interfaces that seem like successful apps, and they're cluttered with bad photographs and graphical effects. This paper describes the importance of usability and HCI principles and guidelines in designing UI of mobile applications. Different procedures that should be followed to conduct a research are also discussed in the paper. The paper also emphasizes on the application of design principles for UI and its evaluation using different HCI techniques and usability testing.

Keywords: *social-media, Human Computer Interaction, mobile application*

I. INTRODUCTION

Clubhouse is an iOS and Android social audio software that allows users to speak in audio chat rooms with thousands of people. On the app, you may choose from a variety of interests to see which "rooms" are currently available and which will be available soon. You can enter a room, listen or contribute (or leave silently) as if you were at a virtual conference or party (depending on your interests). [1]

Clubhouse is directly competed with by other social audio programs such as Discord Stage Channels, Facebook Live Audio Rooms, Reddit Talk, Slack Huddles, Spotify Greenroom, Telegram Voice Chats, and Twitter Spaces. Above all Discord application is closely related with the Clubhouse as it provides a platform where users communicate with voice calls, video calls, text messaging, media and files in private chats or as part of communities.[2] The UI design of the application is quite ambitious as it relies both on the knowledge of world and user's understanding. So, learning to use the app in its full capacity seems complex, especially to a novice user. [3]

Similarly, Twitter spaces is a new way to have live audio conversations on Twitter. Anyone can join,

listen, and speak in a Space on Twitter for iOS and Android. For now, all Spaces are public like Tweets, which means they can be accessed by anyone.[4] They will automatically appear at the top of your Home timeline, and each Space has a link that can be shared publicly. The application has few obvious nice-to-have features, like audience reactions and emoji reactions. Overall, everything fits their UI guidelines and looks really polished and simple to understand. [5]

The hype about Clubhouse is difficult to describe, but the addiction to exposure is apparent. Since the outbreak, the program has sparked the interest of many intellectuals, as well as engaging and mesmerizing users. During the pandemic, the app successfully connected millions of users and provided a space for people to share their thoughts and converse. However, because of its complex approach to UI design and usability, it has lost many loyal users and is not suitable for novice users, and the app is currently unable to maintain its past popularity.

There has been a great deal of study done to improve the application's effectiveness and usability. Many researchers have contributed to the development of the application to make it more user-friendly. Scrolling and categorizing rooms, placing the search bar near the thumb, and rating the quality of the discussion at the end of the room, according to one researcher, could help users learn their preferences faster. [6]

Another study found that iconography, symbolism, and window layout all play a significant role in engaging the user, which Clubhouse lacked. Improved navigation, data categorization, and visual clutter reduction could all help to improve the app, according to a researcher.[8]

After evaluating past research, this study proposes that HCI approaches, as well as usability principles and guidelines should be used in the design process

to create efficient and effective user interfaces that meet the demands and requirements of users.[5] We are using Schneiderman's Eight Golden rules for heuristic evaluation to design and implement a Clubhouse mobile application because it appeared to be the most appropriate strategy through several research and studies.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed method to re-design and implement on Clubhouse application consists of various HCI principles such as Survey, Paper Prototype, Schneiderman's Eight golden rules and usability testing. Then the modified implementation of the design was designed using the Figma application. After all the above steps were implemented we took our completed frontend design for testing from our potential users and gathered their feedback.

A. Survey:

Survey is one of the most important tools used in HCI. It is an extremely easy and cost effective method to gather data from people. We used this method extensively for our application. We conducted a survey on our potential users in the initial phase to gather data for our problem statement. We prepared a questionnaire of 10 questions and conducted a survey with 50 people to gather the user requirements and experience on the present Clubhouse application. We used Google Form as a tool to prepare questionnaires for the survey. We simply sent the link containing the questionnaire to the potential users. We gathered a lot of useful data from this survey which provided a proper roadmap of what we wanted to do with the present layout of Clubhouse.

B. Paper Prototype

Paper prototyping is a widely used method in the user-centered design process that helps developers

to create software that meets the user's expectations and needs especially for designing and testing user interface.[6] After we found our problem statement from the survey, we started to design a paper prototype to modify Clubhouse . The prototype method can be implemented using pen and paper or by using computer software such as Adobe Illustrator. However, we decided to use a traditional pen and paper method for our purpose. We then conducted another survey on our paper prototype so that we can improve it from the feedback of users. We conducted a one on one survey where users were asked to perform some tasks on the paper prototype. In the survey we asked users how easy it was to perform tasks in this prototype and what could be improved. Based on the feedback from the users, there were some improvements and hence a second in some aspects of our UI design.

C. Design:

In the design phase, the system functionality and the development method were finished. After gathering, studying and analyzing system requirements, we converted them into logical system specifications. In logical design, all functional features of the system chosen for development in analysis are described independently of any computer platform. The tool used to design logical system specifications of the application is Use Case Diagram. A use case diagram is a representation of a user's interaction with the system that shows the relationship between the user and the different use cases in which the user is involved. They provide a simplified and graphical representation of what the system must actually do. The purpose of the use case diagram is simply to provide the high-level view of the system and convey the requirements in lay-people's terms for the stakeholders. A use case diagram of the Clubhouse mobile application is given below:

Fig 1: Use Case Diagram

D. Persona

A persona is a model of user that focuses on the individual goals when using a product. The persona model resembles classical user profiles, but with some important distinctions.[10] It is not a description of a real, single or an average user. We created the persona to better understand what kind of user used this type of application. It is extremely important to create an application for the users that actually use them. Persona bound the developer to develop the system based on user preferences. We created a persona for our purpose and it is shown below:

Fig 2: Persona

E. Heuristic Evaluation

The majority of implementation was done addressing the Heuristic evaluation to evaluate the user interface design of Clubhouse. We used Schneiderman's Eight Golden rules [11] for heuristic evaluation. The idea behind heuristic evaluation is that several evaluators independently critique a system to come up with potential usability problems. It is important that there must be several of these evaluators and the evaluation must be done independently. The 8 golden principles are given below:

- Strive for consistency
- Cater to universal usability
- Offer informative feedbacks
- Design Dialogs to yield closure
- Permit easy reversal of actions
- Support internal locus of control
- Reduce short term memory load
- Prevent Errors

After implementing the application using these principles we got some experts to evaluate our design based on these principles. Based on the feedback from the experts we improved our app.

F. Usability testing

Finally we conducted usability testing with our users. Usability testing [12] is done to gather data from the user on how usable our system is. It is done at last to gather feedback from the user on the finished product. There are different tools to conduct usability testing. For our purpose, we used one on one meetings with online surveys to gather data. Google form was used to prepare a questionnaire for our survey. We asked the users to perform some tasks on the designed model and get familiar with it. Then we conducted a survey to gather feedback on their experience using our application.

III. RESULTS

In this section, the results of some of the major phases are discussed and analyzed.

A. Survey:

We acquired diverse data from our users in the initial survey to establish our problem statement. Figure 4 (a, b, and c) demonstrates that more than half of the respondents are male student users between the ages of 18 and 25. Figure (d) illustrates that respondents utilize the application on occasion, indicating that there is significant potential for this type of application right now. However, more than half of those polled said the system's fonts/colors and design were inconvenient, and that the organization of information on the screen was confusing and misleading. Another important conclusion from our initial survey was that more than half of all respondents felt strongly that the system should be redesigned to be more user friendly.

(a)

(b)

Do you think the format of fonts/color throughout the system is convenient?

What is your opinion about organization of information on the screen?

(g)

Fig 3 (a)(b)(c)(d)(e)(f)(g): Responses to our initial survey

B. Paper Prototype:

After the initial prototype was designed, we conducted a survey to gather feedback from the users on our design. There were some positives and some negative feedback. Based on the feedback from the users we improved the design of our paper prototype. Some of the snapshots of our improved paper prototypes are given below:

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig 4(a)(b)(c): Snapshots of our final paper prototype

C. Implementation:

During our implementation we used a front-end designing tool called Figma to design our Clubhouse mobile application which is a minimum viable product (MVP). Keeping Schneiderman's Eight Golden Rules in mind, we executed them. We

also solicited feedback from a number of reviewers who conducted heuristic evaluations on our app. The following are some screenshots of our final application:

(a): Home page

(b): Explore and Chat page

(c): Entering and leaving room Page

(d): User's profile and other's profile Page

(e): Snapshots of our Clubhouse Interface Design

Fig 5(a)(b)(c)(d)(e): Snapshots of our Clubhouse UI Design

D. Usability Testing:

We performed a survey to gather data from our targeted user to find the usability of our application. We prepared questionnaires in a linear scale manner where users were made to rate and judge some aspects of the design. Here, 1 is rated as worst or low, 5 as excellent or high and 3 as average. After studying the summary result of the survey for usability testing, we found that most users felt comfortable and confident to use the redesigned version of Clubhouse. The summary of survey result is shown in the following figures:

how clean and simple is the layout?
21 responses

(a)

Please rate the color combination of the layouts
21 responses

(b)

How easily understandable are the symbols and icons?
21 responses

(c)

How comfortable are you using the application?
21 responses

(d)

How easy is the application for new beginner users?
21 responses

(e)

How easily can you perform the task that you wanted to ?
21 responses

(f)

How often will you now use the app ?
21 responses

(g)

Fig 6: (a)(b)(c)(d)(e)(f): Results of our Usability testing Survey

From the above results, we can list out the major findings of our survey for Usability Testing as follows:

- According to 89% of all respondents, the layout is now clean and simple.
- More than 75% of all respondents thought the system's color selections were better than average, i.e. good.
- More than 90 percent of the respondents agreed that the symbols and icons were simple to understand and consistent.
- Almost 94 percent of all respondents are now excellently confident and comfortable in their ability to use the app.
- The new users can now easily use and understand the system, according to 89 percent of the total respondents.
- Without being confused or lost, 85 percent of responders could easily do the work they desired.
- Finally, 57.1 percent of respondents are willing to use the app more than they have in the past, 33.3 percent are willing to use it on a regular basis, and 9.5% are willing to check it sometimes.

IV. DISCUSSION

After designing and implementing the Clubhouse app using various HCI principles and guidelines such as survey, paper prototyping, heuristic evaluation we have found interesting results in our research. The results found in various phases of our methodology allowed us to design an amazing application that our users found usable and satisfactory.

Survey results were essential in identifying our problem statement and determining what our users wanted from the Clubhouse app. We received input on the intended design of our application through a survey conducted on a paper prototype. The paper prototype was a low-cost way to obtain user input on our app and make changes to the design. In our initial study, the majority of users said they preferred to utilize a 'start a room' button among the other navbar buttons, while others claimed it was confusing. The expert evaluators' feedback was also extremely beneficial, as it allowed us to design

our app strictly following Schneiderman's Eight Golden Rules of Interface Design. Finally, the findings of our usability testing survey assisted us in determining how our users felt about the finished Clubhouse app.

In the sense that user-centered app design always generates a better product that will be used by the majority of users, our research agrees with past research. We implemented fundamental HCI principles and guidelines to build a user-centered application in our study, and we received feedback from users and experts in the area at every stage of the design process.

V. CONCLUSION

This report described a research project in which the popular mobile app Clubhouse was redesigned and implemented utilizing HCI concepts. As evidenced by the results of numerous surveys, usability and HCI concepts in the design of the application were determined to be quite effective. The findings reveal a strong link between a user-centered mobile application and a better product used by the majority of users. The proposed study found that incorporating HCI design principles into an application's design can significantly boost user interest in it. As evidenced by the results, users are more likely to utilize the app regularly.

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